

IOT BASED DUAL AXIS SOLAR TRACKER USING REAL TIME DATA

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ABSTRACT

Solar tracker that aligns itself accurately with the position of the sun using photovoltaic panels, sensors, motors, and a control system. By maximizing the amount of sunlight that reaches the photovoltaic panels, the solar tracker enhances the efficiency and performance of solar energy systems, leading to increased energy production. The sunflower design Solar tracker utilizes Arduino and NodeMCU platforms to adjust parameters like tilting angles for improving efficiency. The control hardware of the solar panel is based on IOT control processes and blynk software. The system uses hardware components such as solar panels, LDR, humidity, voltage and current sensors and solenoid pipes for support systems. Data processing is carried out using additional software such as Arduino IDE and the solar tracking system achieves higher efficiency and energy generation by maintaining the panel perpendicular to the angle of sun rays. Greater efficiency is achieved on dual axis compared to traditional fixed one. The system is more compact able and portable.

Keywords: Solar panel, Arduino UNO, Node MCU, LDR sensors

1. Introduction

With reference to the future period, energy demand will soar while traditional fossil fuel reserves rapidly dwindle. Consequently, tapping into renewable energy sources becomes imperative to meet this escalating demand. Among these sources, solar energy stands out as the most abundant and accessible throughout the year. Solar technology harnesses the sun's energy through photovoltaic (PV) panels, converting solar radiation into electricity. Moreover, PV technology represents a rapidly advancing field requiring minimal maintenance and boasting a zero carbon footprint. However, a PV panel's performance isn't solely reliant on solar irradiance, weather conditions, and ambient temperature; it also hinges on the angle of solar radiation incidence. Throughout the day, the sun's apparent movement from east to west results in a continually changing angle between the sun and a fixed PV surface. Extensive research and experimentation have demonstrated that maintaining consistent direct exposure from the sun to the PV module can significantly enhance power efficiency compared to fixed tilted panels. Implementing dual axis tracking in solar panel system can help in enhancing the efficiency. In this case Sunflower shaped solar tracker is used as shown in Fig 1.

Fig:1 Sunflower based solar panel

Fig 2: Basic mechanism of the working model

Solar trackers are devices used to align PV panels with the sun as shown in Fig 2, which consists of three main types of solar tracking systems: passive, active and open-loop trackers. Passive trackers utilize two canisters filled with compressed gas fluid placed in the east and west of the tracking system. However, these gas trackers often fail to directly point the PV panel towards the sun due to the unpredictable ambient temperatures. Advancements in sensor technology have led to the use of light sensors in active sun tracker systems. These sensors positioned at various locations on the tracker determine the optimal sun position, allowing for precise tilting of PV panels using actuators. Nevertheless, cloud cover and shadows remain significant challenge to the system, resulting in energy wastage as tilting actuators continuously adjust during search mode. The fig 3 represents the opening and closing movement of the dual axis solar panels.

Fig 3: Rotational movement of the panel

1.1 COMPONENTS USED

The table 1.1 represents the various components used in the design and fabrication the solar tracker with its detailed specifications and description.

Table 1.1: Brief description of Components

 <p>SOLAR PANEL</p>	<p>A device that converts sunlight into electrical energy, comprising multiple photovoltaic cells arranged in a panel to generate power. Dimension of solar 99*69mm</p>
 <p>LDR SENSOR</p>	<p>A sensor that changes its resistance based on the intensity of light, commonly used in light-sensitive applications like automatic lighting systems.</p>

<p style="text-align: center;">SERVO MOTOR</p>	<p>A type of motor capable of precise control over angular position, often used in robotics and automation to move parts with accuracy. Torque 10kg/cm at 5v input</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">DC-DC BUCK CONVERTER</p>	<p>A device that converts a higher input voltage to a lower output voltage, commonly used to power electronic devices efficiently.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">ARDUINO UNO</p>	<p>A microcontroller board based on the ATmega328P or ATmega168 chip, providing an open-source platform for programming and controlling electronic projects.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">MOTOR DRIVER</p>	<p>An electronic circuit that controls the speed and direction of a DC motor, commonly used in robotics and automation applications.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">VOLTAGE SENSOR</p>	<p>A sensor that measures the voltage of an electrical circuit, providing feedback for monitoring and control purposes.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">CURRENT SENSOR</p>	<p>A sensor that measures the current flowing through an electrical circuit, used for monitoring and protection in various applications.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">RESISTORS</p>	<p>An electronic component that limits the flow of electric current in a circuit, commonly used to control voltage levels and protect other components. 10k ohm</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">BATTERY</p>	<p>A device that stores chemical energy and converts it into electrical energy, providing portable power for various electronic devices. Capacity: 12V 7amphs</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">NODE MCU ESP-8266</p>	<p>A low-cost open-source IoT platform based on the ESP8266 Wi-Fi module, enabling wireless communication and control in IoT projects.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">JUMP WIRES</p>	<p>Pre-cut wires with connectors at each end, used to connect components on a breadboard or in a circuit without soldering.</p>

1.2WORKING:

In this system, five LDRs are fixed to sense the intensity of light (Two for Azimuth position sensor and another two for Altitude position sensor). The analog signal from the sensors is given to the in-built ADC (Analog to Digital Converter) and light comparison unit. This output is given as an input to the Arduino board along with the input command. The output of the Arduino is given to the motor driving circuit. Two servo motors relate to the driving circuit, one for vertical and another one for horizontal movement. The motor rotates the solar panel perpendicular to the position of sun's rays. The third servo motor used to create the moment of the 12 solar panels dynamically with respectively the presence and absence of sun. The combination of signals is fed to the Arduino and this bit pattern is shown in table 1.2.

Table 1.2: Truth table of light sensor

LDR-1	LDR-2	LDR-3	LDR-4	LDR-5
1	1	1	0	0
0	1	1	1	0
0	0	1	1	1
1	0	1	0	1

When the motor gets the last bit pattern in table 1.2, the motor will move the panel to its initial position and again follow these steps, when sun starts rising in the next day. Even a load is taken from the solar panel by connecting the panel with battery and inverter. The battery is used to store and give the DC supply to the inverter, which is taken from the solar panel.

II LITERATURE

The literature survey provides an overview of existing research and scholarly works relevant to the study, offering insights into the current state of knowledge in the field.

M. Santhosh., et.al [1] discusses the development and deployment of an Internet of Things (IoT) network to track dispersed PV systems, focusing on reducing costs and enhancing efficiency through continuous data collection and monitoring, as well as emphasizing the importance of renewable energy sources and the use of smart grids for reliable and secure power supply. It also presents a specific project involving an Arduino- based solar tracker using LDR and a servo motor, which moves with the sun to optimize solar panel exposure and improve power efficiency. The system interfaces with a cloud platform and uploads data using the Blynk application. G. Pillewar., et.al [2] The paper discusses the increasing energy demand in India, the need for green energy solutions, and the importance of the dual axis solar system project in tracking sunlight intensity for maximum power output. It also emphasizes the significance of dual-axis solar tracking system in maximizing power output in solar energy systems. Ms Ritika Rai., et.al [3] The paper discusses the proposal and design of an IoT-based solar energy monitoring system to collect and analyse solar energy parameters for stable power generation, with the main intention of maximizing power output from solar panels. using WI-FI Module ESP8266 in this system, which allows it to interact with the other sensors and gadgets. This module requires an external logic converter as it not capable of 5V-3V logic shifting the system is designed to ensure stable power generation and predict performance. It also includes a working model of the proposed system. Kaushalya Vaibhav Thopate., et.al [4] summary of the paper is the presentation of a comprehensive and cost-effective solar power monitoring system using NodeMCU and Thing Speak, demonstrating its feasibility and effectiveness, with potential for further improvement through machine learning algorithms and predictive maintenance models, and contributing to the wider adoption of renewable energy sources for a sustainable future. M Rumbayan et.al .,[5] The paper aims to develop an IoT-based monitoring system for solar energy utilization in off-grid solar home systems in remote areas, specifically focusing on Bunaken Island, to provide real-time data and support the operation and maintenance of the off-grid PV system. The study refers to the stages of the method research and development (R&D), indicating a focus on developing effectiveness of

the IoT-based monitoring system, which allows monitoring from any device or computer. The objective of achieving an IoT-enabled monitoring system for small off-grid solar power that can report real-time data has been accomplished. Vinith. S. G., et.al [6] investigates the challenges in harnessing the full potential of solar energy due to factors like dust accumulation on solar panels. Solar energy, abundant and dependable, can be hindered by reduced efficiency caused by environmental elements such as dust, dirt, and weather-related factors. Manual cleaning methods have limitations, including safety concerns, inefficiency, and potential damage to the solar panels. Addressing these issues, the proposed system introduces an automatic cleaning system for solar panels utilizing IoT technology. The system incorporates a programmable device controlled by a micro controller and an Android application, making it portable and reducing the need for manual labour. S Sabitha., et.al., [7] The paper discusses a proposed IoT-based monitoring and maintenance system for solar panels. It aims to prevent damage and faults, addressing issues like hot temperature, pressure, and voltage/current faults. The system utilizes components such as the ESP32 micro controller, voltage and current sensors, pressure and temperature sensors, and a submersible pump with a driver module. The system constantly monitors parameters and takes corrective actions, like activating the submersible pump when faults are detected. The proposed system is claimed to be efficient, with a 95% success rate attributed to the monitoring process. Overall, it aims to save energy, reduce faults, and provide real-time monitoring of power consumption in solar panels. P. Muthukumar., et.al [8] The text discusses the expansion of solar capacity in India and the shift from fixed solar systems to advanced tracking technologies, specifically single- and dual-axis solar trackers. It highlights the efficiency improvements achieved by using solar concentrates and presents tables and Figs comparing the output of fixed solar panels with dual axis tracking panels at various times. The passage explores various solar tracking technologies, including active single-axis trackers and methods involving micro controllers and digital control strategies. It introduces a proposed dual-axis solar tracker system utilizing an IoT platform and a micro controller for optimized energy output. The study aims to address challenges associated with traditional energy sources and emphasizes the advantages of solar energy, dual- axis tracking, and micro controller-based control systems. The methodology outlines steps for data gathering, system development, and IoT-based monitoring, while the working principle describes how the dual-axis solar tracker enhances energy conversion efficiency by optimizing the solar panel's angle of incidence with the sun. Devang Pradeep., et.al [9] The literature survey discusses a dual-axis solar tracking device with a cooling system designed to enhance the efficiency and energy output of solar panels. The system utilizes a micro controller-based tracking mechanism and a cooling system that circulates water through the panels. The integration of dual axis tracking and cooling aims to overcome limitations such as decreased efficiency due to continuous sun exposure and overheating of solar panels. The proposed system shows promise in improving energy output, reducing maintenance costs, and extending panel lifespan. The study highlights the environmental friendliness of technology, contributing to the shift towards sustainable energy. The hardware analysis indicates a preliminary 8% gain in energy output compared to static solar panels. The authors suggest future applications in domestic settings, rural areas, and urban environments with electric vehicles. Further research is recommended to refine the design and optimize cost-benefit ratios for various applications. Muhammad Hanif bin Ishak., et.al [10] The literature survey explores the adoption of an automatic dual- axis solar tracking system to enhance the efficiency of solar photovoltaic panels. It highlights the global shift towards renewable energy and the challenges faced by solar cells in achieving high efficiency. The study introduces a dual-axis tracking system utilizing light-dependent resistors (LDRs) to monitor the sun's movement, aiming to surpass the performance of single-axis trackers. The methodology involves an ESP32 micro controller, Wi-Fi, LDRs, voltage, and current sensors, with two tracking algorithms for comparison. Results show that the dual-axis system consistently outperforms the single-axis system, boasting an 18% increase in efficiency. Lux measurements from LDRs further reveal higher light intensity, contributing to improved energy production. The study concludes that the integration of a dual-axis solar tracking system, with precise sun tracking and IoT capabilities, is a valuable investment for optimizing solar panel performance, providing insights for future design decisions. Mani P K., et.al [11] emphasizes

introducing an IoT-based solar tracking system. It discusses hardware like LDR, voltage/current sensors, solar panel, servo motor, and NodeMCU. Thing Speak is noted as the software platform. The system aims to boost efficiency by adjusting the solar panel based on sunlight. Results display power absorption throughout the day, and conditions for panel rotation are outlined using LDR values. Overall, the proposed system seeks to overcome stable solar panel limitations for improved energy efficiency. The literature emphasizes the global importance of solar energy and introduces diverse solar tracking methods. Key hardware components, including LDRs and sensors, are detailed for efficient solar panel tracking. The proposed system dynamically adjusts the panel to optimize sunlight absorption, addressing limitations of static panels. Ashim Mondal., et.al [12] The literature survey explores the role of the Internet of Things (IoT) in enhancing the quality of life, specifically focusing on solar energy systems. Numerous studies are discussed, each presenting IoT-based solutions for monitoring and managing solar power generation. The highlighted systems utilize micro controllers, such as Node-MCU and Arduino Uno, combined with sensors like current and voltage sensors, DHT11 for temperature and humidity, and Raspberry Pi for inverter monitoring. The proposed architectures leverage IoT for real-time data collection, cloud storage, and remote control, contributing to improved efficiency in solar energy utilization. The hardware components, including BOLT IoT module, Arduino Uno, ACS712ELCTR-30A-T current sensor, voltage sensor, and OLED display, form integral parts of the systems. The literature emphasizes the significance of these IoT-based approaches in addressing challenges and optimizing the performance of solar power systems. Anshul Chandaliya., et.al [13] The literature survey explores the development of a dual-axis solar panel with autonomous solar tracking to improve solar energy efficiency, addressing limitations of stationary panels. Motivated by sustainability, it draws inspiration from heliotrope in sunflowers. Categorizing existing solar technologies, it highlights drawbacks of stationary panels and advantages of single-axis and dual-axis trackers. The methodology involves CAD, 3D printing, Arduino, servo motors, and light sensors. Testing shows a 40% increase in power output for the dual-axis tracker. The study suggests upgrades like servo improvements and machine learning for enhanced functionality, contributing to efficient solar panel technologies and sustainable energy solutions. Kanhaiya Kumar1., et.al [14] The paper discusses the development of a solar positioning system using GPS, artificial neural network (ANN), and image processing (IP) to achieve optimum tracking point for solar panels, aiming to set up a monitoring system with the most economical and precise solar coordinates for maximum efficiency. The proposed system improves power gain by 59.21% and 10.32% compared to stable and two-axis solar following systems, respectively. Aboubakr El Hammoumi., et.al [15] The paper emphasizes on International Telecommunication Union defines the Internet of Things (IoT) as a global infrastructure connecting physical and virtual things to provide advanced services. The IoT encompasses devices that communicate with the Internet using embedded sensors and processors. This chapter explores an IoT-based solar tracker system, optimizing energy production by aligning solar panels with the sun. The proposed system is dual axis, allowing automatic or manual tracking. Few existing attempts integrate IoT monitoring into solar trackers, often using platforms like Ubidots, Thing Speak, or Raspberry Pi.

2.1 BLOCK DIAGRAM:

The Figure 2.1 represents the block diagram of dual axis solar tracker system , which consists of an Arduino board, LDR, DC and servo motors. An input command is given to the Arduino board. Five LDRs are connected to the Arduino. This unit gives signal to the Arduino. The Arduino in turn commands the motor driving circuit to rotate the solar panel in horizontal or vertical position.

Fig 2.1 : Working flow chart

2.2 CIRCUIT DIAGRAM:

The circuit diagram explains the micro controller connections with the servo motors, LDR's and digital display as shown in the Fig 2.2. The micro controller receives data from the LDR sensors which is responsible for the movement of the servo motors.

Fig 2.2: circuit diagram

2.3 CALCULATIONS:

The initial calculation is done by analyzing the dimensions, weight of the individual components and calculating the torque of the required Servo motors. The detailed descriptions are given below,

Servo:

Stall torque value 10kg/cm at 5V.

Solar Panels (12):

Each individual panel weighs 25grams.

$$25 \times 12 = 300$$

Therefore, all solar panels (12) together weigh 300grams.

Solar panels mount (6):

Each individual panel mount weighs 26grams.

$$26 \times 6 = 156$$

Therefore, all panel mounts (6) weighs 156grams.

Rings (6) & Servo mount:

All rings and servo mount together weighs 119grams.

Overall weight of the top components:

Solar panels + solar panel mounts + rings & servo mount

$$300 + 156 + 119 = 575$$

Therefore, the overall top part of the system weighs 575grams.

Calculation of the torque required to drive a mass of 575 grams using a lever arm of 40 mm.

Step 1: To Determine the force exerted by the mass.

Force (F) = mass (m) * acceleration due to gravity (g)

Mass (m) = 575 grams = 0.575 kg

Acceleration due to gravity (g) = 9.8 m/s²

$$F = 0.575 \text{ kg} * 9.8 \text{ m/s}^2$$

$$= 5.645 \text{ N}$$

Step 2: To Calculate the torque.

Torque (τ) = Force (F) * Lever Arm (r)

Lever Arm (r) = 40 mm = 0.04 meters

$$\tau = 5.645 \text{ N} * 0.04 \text{ m}$$

$$\approx 0.2258 \text{ Nm}$$

So, the torque required to drive a mass of 575 grams using a lever arm of 40 mm is approximately 0.2258 Newton-meters.

2.4 Working principle based on C program :

Solar panels to current sensors and voltage sensor the power is then sent to the battery.

OLED display, Servo motors and the LDR sensors are connected to Arduino uno.

Current sensors and the voltage sensors are connected to node MCU.

C programming language is used in Arduino IDE software to track and align the panels.

2.5 TESTING:

Tracking of Lights using LDR's were tested.

Opening and closing of the solar panels were tested according to the calculated torque as shown in Fig2.3.

Fig 2.3: Initial testing

Fig 2.4: Final Tracking

3. Results and Discussion

The Sunflower shaped Dual axis solar tracking system can enhance the energy output by up to approximately 11.58% higher than the efficiency of the fixed solar module. This means that the compact able and portable dual-axis solar tracking system can generate more energy, making it one of the most reliable sources of renewable energy resource.

Table 2.1

TIME	FIXED (V)	DUAL AXIS (V)
7:30	53	62
8:30	55	63
9:30	52	60
10:30	54	62
11:30	58	67
12:30	59	68
13:30	62	71
14:30	61	72
15:30	63	71
16:30	62	71
17:30	61	70
18:30	48	51

Fig 2.5 Graphical representation of readings

- Fixed Solar Panel setup gives 79.62% voltage.
- Dual Axis Solar Panel setup gives 91.2% voltage.
- Overall, the Sunflower shaped dual axis solar tracker gives efficiency of approximately 11.58%.

In addition, the portable sunflower shaped dual-axis solar tracking system can be designed to be lightweight and compact able compared to the traditional solar panels, makes it more convenient for users to travel and set up the system in required locations. This in turn makes it a promising solution for remote areas, camping sites or disaster relief situations where the access to the grid-based electricity is limited or held restricted.

4. CONCLUSION

The sunflower-shaped dual-axis solar tracking system significantly boosts energy output by approximately 11.58% compared to fixed panels. Fabrication utilizes 3-D printing with PLA+ material, ensuring even distribution of impact on the system while tracking. Its compact and portable design allows for efficient utilization of minimal space, outperforming traditional panels. Micro controller codes with PID filters enhance LDR sensor precision in detecting sunlight direction, thus improving efficiency. Integration of current and voltage sensors, along with nano technology linked to blynk software, enables real-time data collection, providing comprehensive system insights.

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